

Role of Marketing Structural Adaptation on Customer Satisfaction: A Case of Zong in Pakistan

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Rashed Nawaz**, Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Hazara University Mansehra

⁽²⁾**Waqar Ahmed**, Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Hazara University Mansehra ⁽³⁾**Muhammad Arshad**,
Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Hazara University Mansehra

⁽⁴⁾**Tayyaba Rani**, Commerce Lecturer, Government College, Faisalabad

⁽⁵⁾**Sabeela Sabir** Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Hazara University Mansehra

⁽⁶⁾**Adnan Khan**, Research Scholar, University of Wales, UK

Abstract

the actual objective of this study is to explore the relationship between the marketing structure and customers in Zong Company. The notion not only attracts most of the customers towards the ZONG but also the reputation of ZONG toppled over other cellular networks. In this research, in this research marketing structure has taken a independent and an independent variable customer satisfaction. The target population was the ZONG customers and employees who were attached with Zong from last four years. In this study 300 customers and 50 employees sample was taken on the basis of simple random sampling. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect the data from the respondents. A simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents. Results of this study explain that there is a strong and positive relationship between structural adaptation and customer satisfaction.

Key words: Marketing Structural Adaptation, Zong

1. Introduction

In the recent era organizations around the globe are working in an open system in which there is a need to maintain some minimal requirements to ensure the effective performance of organization (Porras & Robertson's, 1992). Business organizations are social entities having very complex open systems. For long-term growth and survival, every company needs to adopt environmental changes for enhancing the capabilities and strength of business to provide want-satisfying products to the customers (Melita, 2007). On the other hand, after adaptation, the survival of organization depends upon the space that would be attained by the organization on fitness landscape (Levinthal & Warglien, 1999).

Hrebiniak and Joyce (1985) has further explains two types of adaptation within an organization these are, internal and external adaptation. Internal adaptation changes the administrative structure such as organizational structure, policies and technology etc. While external adaptation causes changes or restructuring in relationship with business partners or business niches etc. It is also reviewed in literature that rivalries, technological changes, bargaining power of suppliers, customers, political and economic integration, demographic trends and social expectations are also the factors that can affect the adaptation process (Jones, 1998; 2004). All these changes are unpredictable and constantly change with the passage of time (McKelvey, 1997), and business organizations need to manage these changes effectively for fulfilling the needs of the customers for their satisfaction.

On the other hand, customer satisfaction has been analyzed and considered as an important factor in the business and management studies in recent decades due to a strong competitive environment in the whole world. The organizations which are making well-established strategies for the internal organization success and also strengthen relation with customers to enhance their satisfaction level are quite successful as compared to other organizations which are not practicing these strategies (Lewis, Richard, 2010).

Customer satisfaction is method of matching consumer needs and wishes with company's marketing policy (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). It is a key indicator to evaluate the success of business. The customers who are satisfied with the company ensure cash flow for that company in future and influence

consumer loyalty. In a turbulent business environment for the growth of market share, companies must recognize that how to fulfill needs of customer because satisfaction is essential for creating lasting relationships with customers (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). Therefore a basic knowledge of factors having an effect on customer satisfaction is of immense importance (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). Telecommunication sector in Pakistan has made incredible development in last few years in Pakistan and many companies are making investment in it (Hashim, 2013). ZONG has made some changes in their structure, but still customers are not satisfied with the performance and efficient services of ZONG.

The ability of telecommunications operators, to adapt successfully according to the customers' need has established itself as one of the most challenging issues in today's dynamic market. Therefore, this research examines the level of satisfaction of customers after structural adaptations of Zong Company, especially focusing on changes in its administrative and marketing structure.

This study in hand would also help the scholars and students for finding important areas to conduct further research in this field.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be explained as an organization's ability to attract and retain maximum customers and to improve a further relationship with the customer for long term (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). It is also frequently viewed as the perception of satisfaction after using products or services of an organization's. In long term customer's satisfaction gives long term benefit to company or organization and also gives competitive edge to the company.

Company that offered qualities of different brands characteristics determine the customer satisfaction's level (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). Customer satisfaction may be defined in terms of customer's expectations and in terms of parameters that associate with satisfaction. According to (Grönroos 1984, Kassim and Asiah Abdullah 2010). According to Zairi (2000) the feeling of accomplishment of inner desires is called satisfaction. There is a strong relation between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty (Oliver, 1998). If the needs and demands of customers fulfill by the service or product then the customer will be loyal and satisfied. Profitability of company not only measures in its balance sheet but also in terms of sound customer base and on a value that is delivered by customer to company. The author suggests in his study that customer satisfaction is a basic and core philosophy of marketing strategy for any organization and also plays an important role in the success of any company (Oliver 2014). In fact customer satisfaction is basic and core principle of the modern tool for CRM being used by marketers to retain customers.

Customer's high-level satisfaction is usually customarily believed which create as a general affective result of the application of some sort of products or services which customer used (Leiss, Kline et al. 1990). Customer satisfaction level is highly correlated with the emotional and functional level of the product and services of a company which he used.

Customer fulfillment is concerned with encounters or those functions which a company product and services features give to customers (Kumar, Scheer et al. 2000). The greater the customer satisfaction level, the greater will be relationship and customer attraction and retention level. Furthermore (Flint, Blocker et al. 2011) explained that there is a positive and strong relationship between fulfillment and also devotion of the customer which he perceived from the greater performance of company product or services.

Customer is the main and important factor for every company because the success and failure of the company in the local and international market depends on the satisfaction level of the customers. As company expends huge amount on the advertisement, product, R&D and other services to attract the customers and sell out their products and services (Fullerton, & Wempe, 2009). It has been experienced in so many companies that their administration totally ignores the importance of the product and services quality and ultimately causes a great loss for the company and also customer satisfaction leads towards dissatisfaction (Hill & Alexander, 2001). On the other side Wilson (2002) argues that customer satisfaction is confusing and complex in nature,

and is mostly composed of different factors which can be measured in a different way in different situations. It means that customers' satisfaction level varies from condition to condition.

Tiwari and Buse (2007) stated in their research work that every business either it is a small business or huge it depends upon the organization policies that how it effectively implement those strategies which are beneficial both for the customer and organization.

Customer satisfaction can be operationalized as, how a customer is emotionally and functionally satisfied by using the products and services of any organization. In the other words, it can be said that how a customer perceived positively about the products and services of a company (Jusoh, & Parnell, 2008).

The production of products and services at the bulk level and supply of products and services is no longer the sole purpose of economic activities, achieving the main objectives of the public and private institutions are connected largely to ensuring customer satisfaction. Thus, the main aim of institutions, whether private or public, is not only to 'sell' or provide products or services to citizens, but also to meet the high degree of requirements and needs of consumers, users or citizens (Roboca, Iazar & Solomon, 2009).

The importance of customer satisfaction, generally speaking, lies in the recognition of the method and manner in which organizations, whether private or public, create 'comfort' among both citizens and consumers of products or services, as well as among the suppliers of such services or products (Hill & Alexander, 2001). Customers are the backbone of an organization. Without them, there would be no sales, no profits, no organization, and no business because they are the major sources who generate sales process (Fullerton & Wempe, 2009). They keep an eye on the business activities and contribute to modification and innovation in the company product and services which in return gives a company a strong relationship and long term benefit (Dauw, Su-Yan & Lee, 2013).

Sometimes companies consider that they are doing their best to customer services but in reality it is not so and customers perceive it differently therefore, successful company should handle and manage customers properly (Kotler, 1991). Satisfaction can be briefly explained as that it is a person's feelings of liking or dissatisfaction resulting from using company products or comparing products of the company with other company and compare the product performance and what he/she perceived at that time (Deanfield & Marmot, 2003).

Customer satisfaction is explained by different authors as that it is an attitude or judgment of the customer towards a products or services by purchasing or consuming the product or services (Rust, & Zahorik, 1993)). It means that customer services rose on the emotional and functional satisfaction of customer by using it to achieve his ultimate aim.

Customer satisfaction is the pre and post evaluation of the products and services. When a customer used the product or service to get his pre and post measurement of attributes of the company products or services performance (Rust & Oliver, 1994).

On the other hand, Boateng (2006) states that Satisfaction is simply the result of those which are not going wrong in the favor of the customer satisfaction level.

According to (Flint, Blocker et al. 2011)satisfaction is "The process of customer overall subjective evaluation of the product/service quality against his/her expectation or desires over a time period.

The researchers also defined the satisfaction as, the customers' appraisal of a product or service by using it for a time being and then perceived that either product or services is fulfilling his/her needs(Flint, Blocker et al. 2011). The satisfaction of the customer is usually assumed to be an important factor for the increase of sales, effective word of mouth and the satisfaction of customers. Satisfied customers are more loyal as well as inform other customer regarding their knowledge about company (Hallowell 1996).

Mohammed (2012) explored that if the customer is financially satisfied with the company products and services he/she can be loyal to the company otherwise just services can't guarantee for the retention of the customers' loyalty to the company So it is necessary element that organization should also ensure the financial aspect of the customer, product and services prices should be as according to the buying power of the customers.

Every organization has core values is to create value for the customers in the aspect of products or services. Organization adopt such type of strategies which offering benefits for the customers which are different as compare to its competitors (Piercy 1998). So it is a necessary element for all organization to adopt their strategies as according to current need of the customers, if the customer is agree and satisfy it will ultimately benefit the organization as a whole.

2.2 Marketing Structural Adaptation

Teddle and Tashakkori (2009) studied that Marketing 4 Ps play an important role in the marketing structure. If the marketing structure is established as according to the 4ps it can build a strong relationship with the customer. They further explained that the satisfaction level of the customers is directly related to the marketing mix.

Pride and Ferrell (2011) explored in their study related to marketing structure on the internet that marketing structure is important for an organization to gain international standard to meet the customer need and want at the national and international level.

Kotler and Armstrong (2011) explained that marketing structure has a positive and strong link with customer satisfaction. These two researchers explain this relationship on the basis of a strong relationship between marketing structure and customer satisfaction.

Rysman and Busse (2004) analyzed that there is a significant effect of marketing structure on the shape of the advertising price schedules and it also affects the customers' satisfaction level. On the other hand, McManus (2003) provides empirical evidence for the effect of marketing structure on customer satisfaction stating that marketing structuring depends on the customer demand and satisfaction level.

As far as the literature available in the marketing history that is related to the structural changes shows, marketing is focused process in structural change. First focus is related to the retailing theory (McNair, 1958) and according to this theory Hollander (1966) defines the cyclical patterns of change in channel institutions. These theories provide support to understand some processes of structural adaptation; these theories provide only partial explanation in this regard. These theories mainly deal with and are based on closed-ended system and ignore the main component or driver of change that is interaction with external environment (Eatger, 1984).

The second focus of the historical marketing structure in literature with respect to adaptation process is on the process of innovation; a new form of organizations and changing in distribution channels. At this stage, the focus is only on time needed to implement these changes or time spent for adaptation. There is no information available on why sometimes that adaptation process is succeeded and why sometimes it fails (Wilkinson, 1999).

In the marketing structure, the role of relationship marketing has a great importance for the adaptation of sellers to customers system and procedures so that maximum customers can be attracted by the organization (Morris, Brunyee & Page, 1998). With relationship marketing Strategy Company or any organization can build a strong relationship with their current and old customers to get maximum profit.

Different researchers study argue that in the 1990s, there have been a number of work that explains that the future of marketing structure with respect to organization change (Achrol 1991; Berthon, Hulbert, & Pitt 1997; Cravens 1995; Day, 1997; Doyle, 1995; George, 1994; Webster, 1992; 1997). These studies provided different themes in different adaptation processes.

The marketing management process in structural adaptation is most important to improve the life of the organization (Ciuhureanu, Marcu, Balteş, 2010). If the organization is not approaching in a significant way towards its target in marketing of its products and service, then it will not be able to achieve organization strategic and also short term goal. There are different threats and successes of different organization had taken places in different selection areas, through which most of the employees of the organization involved themselves in the different decisions of the organization, as according to the different authors study observation it can be concluded that different marketing strategies need training and communication skills to improve the organization and its employees' relationships and also trust between these two bother will be fruitful in long run (Kotler, Dipak, Maesincee., 2004) . Different theorists' (Mahoney & Weitzel, 1969; Price, 1968; Yuchtman & Seashore, 1967) studies state that marketing administration is changing with the passage of

time as according to the structural adaptation of the organization in different areas. It means that these two variables have a strong relationship with each other.

Hashim (2013) argues that every organization has an ultimate target is to satisfy his customer, so ZONG has also a target that we will attract and satisfy his customers' maximum to get competitive advantages as compare to other competitors in the market. Hashim study also elaborate that structural changes in Zong has brought significant improvement in ZONG income and also maximum new customers' attracted toward the Zong. Zong has bring a diverse improvement in the pakcgaes

Stone, (2000) and Thompson (2004) explained that structural changes in the organization can lead to the organization level as well as towards the change in the employees' satisfaction level. These researchers concluded results from their research study that changes in the organization structure give benefit to the organization in a strategic way, first one is that organization get a strategic position as compare to those other organizations which are the competitors of the organization.

Conway and Huffcut (2003) in their study state that customer satisfaction level increase in most of the organizations after structural changes in it. They further explained that some factors are which gave a significant contribution in the structural changes; these are technological changes in the world, customers switching from one company to the other and also organization employees turnover effects the organization structural changes.

Parasuraman, Zenithal and Berry (1985) in their study argue that customer satisfaction on the basis of the perception and expectation mostly change the organization system which can be attractive one for the customer, so that's why organization easily adapted themselves as according to the new demand of the customers and some changes in the organization need to develop which ultimately provide a way for little bit structural change in different organizations.

Organization either it is on the small or huge level, every time need changes as according to altering the positioning of the market and customer, consumers, and supplier (OECD, 2001). With the passage of time due to changes in the organization structure different administrative, human resource management, research and development, finance department and marketing administration department took place. All these changes are the gradual and slow process for the satisfaction of the main stakeholders of the company.

3. Research Design

In this research 20 items were included in this research to measure the marketing structure and customer satisfaction. Five-point Likert scales were used to measure the customer satisfaction level. Data were collected from 108 old and 142 new customers of Zong and 50 employees of the company. Simple sampling technique was used to collect the data from the respondents. Pilot study was also conducted for the validity and reliability of the data.

H1: Marketing structural Adaptation has a positive and significant relationship with the customer satisfaction.

The current study is quantitative in nature. The survey method was used to collect the data from the respondents.

Pilot study was conducted to check the validity of the data.

4. Discussion

This study declared that marketing structure and its impact on the customer satisfaction within Zong is still at an explorative stage. There is further need to elaborate the Zong marketing strategies. As Song started its operation in Pakistan since 2008. Before since 2008 it was present in Pakistan a Packtel Compny, but with the new name it showed tremendous results in the market in Pakistan. Now Zong has become a leading cellular Company in Pakistan. Most of the customers are going towards Zong. This is all about due to Zong new marketing strategies like (call Packages, 2G, 3G, and 4G internet facilities).

The result of the study explains that 65% change in the customer satisfaction is due to Zong Company in Pakistan. A change in the independent variables brings a significant and positive change in the dependent variable customer satisfaction from this it is cleared that there is a significant relationship between the

marketing structure and customer satisfaction. The other cellular companies should also learn from the experiences of the Zong.

It was observed that 90 % new customers of Zong were satisfied with the marketing functions of the company and 10 % has some issues like signals problem, hidden charges of calls. So there is a strong need to address this problem. The study also explains that Zong employees are also satisfied with Zong. Employees, satisfaction has improved the marketing structure of the Zong. This study can also be study for including new variables administrative structure.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to recognize the relationship between marketing structure and customers' satisfaction in Zong cellular company. From study findings, it is clear that there is a significant relationship between marketing structure and customer's satisfaction. Most of the customers responded that marketing structure in Zong brought a significant contribution to customers' satisfaction level. Customers' responses explain that marketing structure has a strong relationship with the customers' satisfaction level.

In these study findings, it is evident that a positive and productive change occurs in the mind of the customers due to the marketing structural changes Zong Company. Its capability, relationship quality, coordination, and psychological safety level have increased due to structural change in the Company. The study findings also concluded that strong coordination is necessary for customer satisfaction for the company success.

After applying regression analysis test results indicates that marketing structure plays a significant contribution in the customer satisfaction level. The study explains Zong offer attractive packages to the customer, so customer preference for Zong has increased.

Lastly, there are some recommendations for the future research and ZONG administration that they can enhance further the role of ZONG in a market and attract most of the customers. It is also recommended that if the current initiative of the company remained, in the same way, it will benefit the organization in the long run. Company should change themselves as according to new environmental global change in the world.

The ZONG administration should motivate the customer by different packages of calls, network services and other services to get its previous position in the market where different strong competitors are already working. ZONG's high authority should train their employees to meet the challenges of the market and to save themselves and also secure the future of the company by developing effective strategic plans.

Lastly company should also build the trust of the employees for the better productivity of the employees. There is a strong need of coordination among the customer, administration and employees of the Zong Company. Now Zong is the market leader but further improvement is needed for best and productive results.

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Annexure A

Regression Analysis Table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
	.662 ^a	.438	.412	1.21308	.000

Number of Respondents

Old Customers	108	43%
New Customers	142	56%
Number of Employees	50	All new and old customer were included
Old Customers	108	43%
New Customers	142	56%

Respondents Education of Employees

M.Phil/P.hD	2
MBA	10
B.Com/BA	18
F.A, F.Sc or D.Com	12
Matric	8
Total	50